

Therapeutic effects of silver nanoparticles loaded with albendazole, mebendazole drugs in male albino mice infected with hydatid cysts

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Received: 16 October 2020

Accepted: 26 October 2020

Published: 27 October 2020

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ABSTRACT

The current study was conducted for the period from September 2019 to February 2020 in the Department of Biology-College of Education for Girls-University of Kufa, which aimed to evaluate the therapeutic effects of the silver nanoparticles loaded with albendazole, mebendazole drugs on male albino mice infected with hydatid cysts. The results of the current study showed a significant decrease of $p \leq 0.05$ in the rates of body, liver and spleen weights in all mice of the study groups compared to the positive control. The lowest decrease was in the group of infected mice treated with the hybrid albendazole (Alb + AgNPs). Also, a significant decrease was observed, $p \leq 0.05$, in the average number of hydatid cysts in all study groups compared to the positive control. The hybrid albendazole was the most therapeutic efficacy in inhibiting the growth of the hydatid cysts, followed by the hybrid mebendazole and then the free silver nanoparticles. The success of the synergistic action between free nanoparticles and drugs with the least amount of the drug and the nanoparticle was loading.

Keywords Hydatid cysts, Albendazole, Mebendazole, Silver nanoparticles

1. Introduction

Hydatid cystic disease is the common name for this disease in humans and animals, as the name was adopted according to the general shape and outward appearance of the cyst, and it was noticed that the cyst was filled with water [1]. Echinococcosis is primarily derived from the genus name of the parasite Echinococcus Granulosus because the head of these worms has spines or hooks [2]. Echinococcosis is one of the important health problems because cysts by their nature develop in different body organs [3] as this parasite can reach any organ in the human body when eating food and drink contaminated with the parasite eggs, which are the infected phase that develops inside the body mainly in the liver and lungs into hydatid cysts [4]. Echinococcosis granulosus need two hosts to complete their life cycle, as carnivorous animals, including canidae species, are the first host, which is the definitive host, and herbivorous animals such as cattle, such as cows, sheep, horses, and camels, which represent the intermediate host. The human being also represents an accidental host or Aberrant, as it causes disruption and discontinuity in the life cycle [5]. The geographical distribution of the disease depends on the spread of the final hosts of the parasite. The cause of the spread of hydatid cystic disease can be attributed to two reasons. The first is the inability to detect the infection in the early stages because it does not show pathological symptoms until after the cyst increases in size, which leads to pressure on the surrounding tissues, and the second reason is the loss of treatment methods, and this disease is similar in severity of its spread carcinomas in the metastatic stage [3]. Because of the severity of the disease and the significant health, economic and social implications it poses on humans, researchers have sought to find many treatment methods to eliminate it [6]. The benzimidazole derivatives that are albendazole and mebendazole one of the most effective drugs in eradicating the disease in its early stages by penetrating the cyst and killing the protoscolices, brood capsule and germinal layer [7].

Surgical intervention is one of the best treatment methods for hydatid cysts despite its difficulty or inability to implement it sometimes, or because of the presence of hard-to-reach cysts such as cysts of the brain, spinal cord and heart, or those patients who are difficult to perform operations for such as patients with diabetes [8, 9]. This is what led to thinking about new treatment methods that are more effective and less harmful, and among these methods is the use of nanotechnology [10].

Nanomaterials have multiple properties, including two-dimensional properties, or the so-called Nano sheets, which have gained them a lot of interest due to their unique physical and chemical advantages, including excellent intercalation of cells, which provided new opportunities for the development of different materials in the nanoscale or so-called nanoparticle. The type of compounds provides a variety of applications for this technology in the medical and biological sciences through ion exchange, stimulation, encapsulation and other characteristics [11]. The development of nanotechnology has contributed to changing the medical rules used in preventing; diagnosing and treating diseases and we are living in the era of Nano medical technology. For example, nanotechnology offers new ways for drug carriers inside the body (Nano carriers) with sizes up to the Nano scale are able to target different cells in the body [12]. The current study aimed to evaluate the therapeutic effects of the silver nanoparticles loaded with albendazole, mebendazole drugs on male albino mice infected with hydatid cysts.

2. Materials and Methods

The current study was conducted for the period from September 2019 to February 2020 in the Department of Biology-College of Education for Girls-University of Kufa. The silver nanocomposite was prepared according to the method described before [13] as follows:

1. Dissolve 0.0285 g of sodium borohydride in 10 ml of deionized water in an ice-cold bath, (solution No. 1).
2. 0.4 mg of pyrrolidone polyvinyl was added to the first solution as a stabilizer.
3. Dissolve 0.0214 g of silver nitrate in 10 ml of distilled water (solution No. 2).
4. Solution No. 2 (silver nitrate) was added to Solution No. 1 by patching.
5. Put the flask containing the final solution on the magnetic stirrer for 60 minutes at a temperature of 50-60°C at 1500rpm to turn the resulting solution to a brownish-black color.
6. After that, the solution was left to cool down and washed with distilled water and the process was repeated three times, after which the solution was dried in a thermal furnace and the product was collected and preserved until use in the drug loading process.

The drugs albendazole and mebendazole were loaded onto the silver nanocomposite according to [14] as follows: (1) mg was weighed from the powder of each of the drugs albendazole and mebendazole and added to (1) mg of the free silver nanoparticles after dissolving it in (10) ml of distilled water. Then the mixture was placed on the Magnetic stirrer for (24) hours and then concentrated and dried by rotary evaporator and preserved for the purpose of diagnosis and preparation of therapeutic doses. Hybrid nanoparticles were diagnosed by Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) and X-ray diffraction (XRD), as well as the use of atomic force microscope (AFM) and scanning electron microscope (SEM).

The method described by [15] in a study that the therapeutic substance was released into a solution of carbonate and hydrochloric acid. The ultraviolet ray spectrometer was used to study the release kinetics of the treatment into two types

of solutions, including sodium carbonate at a concentration of (0.5) mole , and the acidic solution with a pH (2). The pH of the acid was modified using hydrochloric acid. 1 mg of the hybrid nanoparticles was added to 3.5 ml of each of the two solutions referred to above, and the absorption of it was measured at the maximum absorption value of the anion (treatment), and the increase in the amount of absorption was followed up in different time periods to find the reaction rank and determine the highest speed of release of the therapeutic substance.

The therapeutic dose was calculated for each of the free nanoparticles and the free and hybrid drugs according to [16] and according to the body weight of the animal, as a dose of 1.5 mg / ml was prepared from the free silver nanoparticles, and hybrid albendazole and mebendazole drugs and the dose of 3.75 mg / ml for both free albendazole and mebendazole drugs, using physiological saline 0.9 % as a solvent [17]. Livers samples of sheep infected with hydatid cysts were obtained from the massacre in Najaf province [18]. Method was adopted to collect the protoscolices, and their viability was examined using 0.1% aqueous eosin stain [19].

In this study, 70 male albino Balbs /c mice, were used, which were divided into the following groups:

- 60 mice were infected with the protoscolices of the Echinococcus Granulosus, at a rate of 2000 ± 10 protoscolex per ml of 0.9% physiological saline solution for each animal. Infection was carried out intraperitoneal and only once [20].
- 10 mice not infected with protoscolices, as it was considered negative control, as they were treated with physiological saline solution 0.9% at 1 milliliter per mouse and through the peritoneum. After 12 weeks of infection, the infected mice (60) were divided randomly into six groups [17].
- 10 mice infected and untreated (positive control).
- 10 mice were infected and treated with free silver nanoparticles at a dose of (1.5) mg/ml per mouse orally
- 10 mice infected and treated with free albendazole at a dose of (3.75) mg/ml per mouse orally.
- 10 mice were infected and treated with free mebendazole at a dose of (3.75) mg/ml per mouse orally.
- 10 mice were infected and treated with silver nanoparticles loaded with albendazole at a dose of (1.5) mg / ml per mouse orally.
- 10 mice were infected and treated with silver nanoparticles loaded with mebendazole at a dose of (1.5) mg / ml per mouse orally.

The treatment was by using an oral dosing device three times a week for a period of 12 weeks. After the end of the treatment period, the mice of each group were anesthetized with diethyl ether. Mice were dissected and the internal viscera were examined, as the location of the cysts was observed, according to their number, and the relative therapeutic efficacy was calculated according to the formula mentioned in a study conducted by [21].

2.1. Statistical analysis

The results were analyzed statistically using the program (SPSS) version 22, and the less significant difference test (L.S.D.) was used in the study to find out the significant differences between the study groups at $P \leq 0.05$ [22].

3. Results and discussion

The results in Table 1 showed that there was a significant increase of $P \leq 0.05$ in the rates of body, liver and spleen weights in the positive control group, as it reached (33.24 ± 1.901 , 2.937 ± 0.310 , 0.369 ± 0.025) gm. respectively, compared with the negative control group was (28.178 ± 1.022 , 2.119 ± 0.292 , 0.25 ± 0.028) gm. respectively.

Some studies reported that the cause of increased body weight and enlarged liver and spleen in the positive control group may be due to the occurrence of infection and the large number of granulomas resulting from infiltration of inflammatory cells in these organs as a result of infection with this disease. This is confirmed by [23], who indicated that one of the most important causes of splenomegaly is the proliferation of lymphocytes as a result of their division and the effect of activation and their secretion of cellular kinetics, which is a natural result of the spleen being the largest lymph organ in the human body that has the ability to produce specific antibodies with parasite antigens.

The results of the current study also showed that the silver nanoparticles and the drugs loaded on them had a significant effect in reducing the rates of body, liver and spleen weights in all treatments compared with the positive control. The lowest decrease was in the (Alb + Ag) group, which was (28.744 ± 1.363 , 2.146 ± 0.167 , 0.27 ± 0.028) gm. respectively, compared to positive control group. The reason for this is due to the presence of active materials in the nanoparticles that have the ability to penetrate the laminated and germinal layers after accumulating around the cyst and causing them to break into its wall, and this leads to a reduction of granuloma and a reduction in the weight of the affected organ [17]. Also, the decrease in weights of the liver and spleen may be due to the reduction of the number of cysts in these organs, and sometimes the absence of cysts in them, and then the decrease in granulomas [24], found that the use of Silver NPs in many concentrations showed great effectiveness in killing protoscolices by 93% compared to the rest of the nanoparticles, including Zn-NPs, Si-NPs and Cu-NPs, and through this study the researchers concluded that Silver nanoparticles is a lethal agent for the Echinococcus Granulosus parasite and that the hybridized nanoparticles of albendazole on ABZ-chitosan nanoparticles when administered as an oral solution for treating mice infected with hydatid cyst was able to effectively spread inside the body, especially within the affected liver tissue, by 222.15% greater than

the group treated with albendazole suspension 146.0% [25, 26], found that the group of mice treated with an emulsifier nano zataria, by oral dosing, reduced the cyst size by 80% compared to the untreated positive control group, which was reflected in the weight of the affected organ and the weight of the animal. Due to the poor solubility of the albendazole and praziquantel in water, which often leads to insufficient therapeutic results, many researchers have resorted to discovering and creating a new formula for these two drugs. These two drugs were loaded on nanoparticles such as chitosan and their effect on the protoscolices was evaluated in vitro and in vivo on infected mice. The results showed that the two drugs, the hybrid or combined with the nanoparticles (ABZ + CH), (PZQ + CH) were more effective than their free formulation as a suspension in killing the protoscolices in vitro and in vivo. They were very effective in reducing the number and size of hydatid cysts compared to their formulation in suspension [27].

Treatments	Body weight gm. M ± SD	Liver weight gm. M ± SD	Spleen weight gm. M ± SD
Negative control	28.178±1.022	2.119 ± 0.292	0.25 ± 0.028
Positive control	33.24 ± 1.901	2.937 ± 0.310	0.369 ± 0.025
Free AgNPs	0.794±29.143	2.204 ± 0.183	0.3 ± 0.053
AgNPs + Alb	28.744 ± 1.363	2.146 ± 0.167	0.27 ± 0.028
AgNPs + Meb	28.896 ± 1.162	2.153 ± 0.228	0.279 ± 0.034
Albendazole	29.835±0.411	2.435± 0.135	0.317 ± 0.042
Mebendazole	30.084 ± 0.472	2.491± 0.292	0.325 ± 0.045
L.S.D	1.008	0.213	0.02

Table 1 Average body, liver and spleen weights for male albino mice treated with free silver nanoparticles, free hybrid drugs of albendazole and mebendazole.

The results in Table 2 showed that the free silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and the drugs loaded on it ALb + AgNPs and Meb + AgNPs and the free drugs albendazole and mebendazole had a significant effect of $P \leq 0.05$ in reducing the average number of hydatid cysts compared to the positive control. The hybrid nanoparticle, (ALb + AgNPs), had a relatively high therapeutic efficacy in reducing the number of cysts, followed by Meb + AgNPs, free AgNPs, free Alb and free Meb, which were 100%, 98.5%, 92.6%, 77.9% and 72.1%, respectively. The absence or lack of secondary hydatid cysts in the study group mice is due to the possession of free and hybrid nanoparticles with high efficiency in destroying the protoscolices by 100% [28].

Treatments	Number of hydatid cysts SD±M	% of therapeutic efficacy
Negative control	0 ± 0	–
Positive control	6.8 ± 3.733	–
Free Ag NPs	0.5± 0.14	92.6
Alb+Ag NPs	0 ± 0	100
Meb +Ag NPs	0.1± 0.02	98.5
Albendazole	1.5±0.4	77.9
Mebendazole	1.9 ± 0.2	72.1
L.S.D.	0.75	

Table 2 Number of hydatid cysts and percentage of therapeutic efficacy in male albino mice treated with free nanoparticles silver, free and hybrid albendazole and mebendazole.

It is considered one of the ideal systems for the delivery of treatment and the concentration of active substances present in chemical treatments in the areas of infection [29, 30] also mentioned that these nanoparticles loaded with the treatment have the ability to penetrate the germ layers of the cyst and biological barriers and protect the drug from the influence of the lysing enzymes and reach the target diseased cells with high stability and also can control their release with the time of release [31], also confirmed that the hybrid albendazole or loaded on some nanoparticles has a high ability to reduce the size and weight of the cysts and increase the concentration of albendazole sulphoxide in blood plasma and liver tissues by 93% compared to normal cases when used in its free form in terms of availability its low biological permeability, poor cellular permeability, indeterminate distribution, and rapid excretion outside the body reduce its

therapeutic efficacy against this disease. It is worth noting that the hybrid nanoparticles of albendazole - chitosan has a more inhibitory effect on the weight and size of the hydatid cysts caused by *Echinococcus Multilocularis* than in the case of cysts treated with the albendazole in the form of tablets, as the nanoparticles caused the breakdown and rupture of both the germinal and laminated layers of the hydatid cysts in liver [17]. It was observed that there was a significant decrease in the weight, size, and number of hydatid cysts of *Echinococcus Granulosus* in mice when treated with the flubendazole (FLBZ) loaded on polyethylene glycol-poly-caprolactuan (PEG-PCL) by 94.64% compared to the group treated with the same free formulation (FLBZ), when it reached 70.21% [32]. It is worth noting that the nanoparticles loaded with albendazole about 300 nm also have great efficiency in diffusion through the cyst membrane and increase the drug concentration in the cyst environment, and it also has the ability to increase the solubility of albendazole and improve the diffusion of the drug from nanoparticles across the hydatid cyst membrane compared to the oral suspension type of albendazole [33]. The conclusion from this study that the free and hybrid nanoparticles act as an inhibitory factor for the growth of hydatid cysts, which leads to greatly improving the efficacy of the therapeutic drugs, albendazole and mebendazole, which indicates the success of the synergistic action between free nanoparticles and drugs with the least amount of the drug and the nanoparticle upon loading.

4. Conclusions

Free and hybrid nanocomposites act as an inhibitory factor for the growth of cysts, which leads to greatly improving the efficiency of the drugs albendazole and mebendazole, which indicates the success of the synergistic action between the nanocomposites and drugs with the lowest amount of the drug and the nanocomposite upon loading and the hybrid nano albendazole drug was the most efficient in reducing the number hydatid cysts, followed by mebendazole, a hybrid nanoparticle, and then free nanoparticles.

Conflict of Interest

The authors report no conflict of interest.

Funding

This study had no financial support.

References

- [1] Casaravilla C, Malgor R, and Carmona C, (2003). Characterization of carbohydrates of adult *Echinococcus granulosus* by lectin-binding alysis. *Journal of Parasitology*, 89: 57-61.
- [2] Kotpal R. L, (1996). Helminthes a textbook for college and university students. *Rastogi Publication*, New Delhi.
- [3] Eckert J, and Deplazes P, (2004). Biological epidemiological and clinical aspects of echinococcosis a zoonosis of increasing concern. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, 17: 107-135.
- [4] Mandal S, and Mandal M.D, (2012). Human cystic echinococcosis epidemiologic, zoonotic, clinical, diagnostic and therapeutic aspects. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine*, 4: 235-260.
- [5] McManus D.P, Zhang W, Li J, and Bartley P.B, (2003). Echinococcosis. *Lancet*, 362: 1295-130.
- [6] Kadir M. A, and Saaid L. A, (1997). The effect of albendazole and mebendazole on *Echinococcus granulosus* protoscolices. *Tikrit University College of Medicine*, 3: 115-120.
- [7] Chinnery J. B, and Morris D. L, (1986). Effect of albendazole sulphoxide on viability of hydatid protoscolices *in vitro*. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygien*, 80: 815-817.
- [8] Zeibig E. A, (1997). Clinical parasitology. 1st ed. W. B. saunders company. *Philadelphia*, 195-202.
- [9] Menten A, Yalaz S, Killi R, and Altintas N, (2000). Radical treatment for hepatic echinococcosis. *Hepato-Pancreato-Biliary*, 2: 49-54.
- [10] Vijayakumar S, Vinoj G, Alaikozhundan M.B, Shanthi S, and Vaseeharan B, (2015). Plectranthus amboinicus leaf extract mediated synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles and its control of methicillin resistant staphylococcus aureus biofilm and blood sucking mosquito larva spectrochim. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 137: 886-891.
- [11] Borm P.J, Robbins D, Haubold S, Kuhlbusch T, Fissan H, Donaldson K, Schins R, Stone V, Kreyling W, Lademann J, Krutmann J, Warheit D, and Oberdorster E, (2006). The potential risks of nanomaterials: a review carried out for ECETOC, Part. *Fibre Toxicology*, 3: 11-46.
- [12] Nalawade P, Aware B, Kadam V.J and Hirlekar R.S, (2009). Layered double hydroxides: A review. *Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research*, 68: 267-272.
- [13] Zhu J, Kan C, Wang J.G and Wang M.H, (2011). High yield of uniform synthesis Ag nano wire high aspect ratio by introducing the long chain pvp in an improved polyol process. *Journal of Nanomaterials*, 7: 122-133.
- [14] Derayea S.M, Ali H.R.H, Hamad A.A and Ali R, (2017). Application of silver nanoparticles for the spectrophotometric determination of three benzimidazole anthelmintic drugs in their pharmaceutical preparation. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, 7: 076-082.

- [15] Wang L, Liu Y, Zhang W, Chen X, Yang T and Ma G (2013). Microspheres and microcapsules for protein delivery: strategies of drug activity retention. *Current Pharmaceutical Design*, 19: 6340-6352.
- [16] Nair A.B and Jacob S (2016). A simple practice guide for dose conversion between animals and human. *Journal of Basic and Clinical Physiology and Pharmacology's*, 72: 27–31.
- [17] Abulaihaiti M, Weiwu X, Qiao L, Lang Lv H, Weizhang H, Aduwayi N, Wang Y, Wang X and Peng X (2015). Efficacy of albendazole – chitosan microsphere –based treatment for alveolar echinococcosis in mice. *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 9: e0003950.
- [18] Smyth J.D (1985). In vitro culture of Echinococcus spp. Proc. 13th. *International Cong Hydatid Madrid*. 84-95.
- [19] Landa-Garacia J.I, Alonso E, Gonzalez-Uriarte J and Roderigues-Romano D (1997). Evaluation of scolicidal agents in experimental hydatid disease model. *European Surgical Research*, 29: 202-208.
- [20] Al-Omorani A.H, Emman G and Altaif K.I (1995). Immunoprophylaxis with Nocardia asteroides cell wall extracts of experimental hydatidosis in Balb/c mice. *Dirasat Agricultural Sciences*, 3: 189-198 .
- [21] Xiao S, Feng J, Guo H and Yao M (1995). Effects of mebendazole, albendazole and praziquantel on alanine aminotransferase and aspartate aminotransferase of Echinococcus granulosus cyst wall harbored in mice. *Acta Pharmacological Sinica*, 2:107-110.
- [22] Morgan G.A, Leech N.A, Gloecner G.W and Barrett K.C (2010). SPSS for introductory statistic use and interpretation 2nd ed. *Lawrence Erlbaum associates, publishers Mahwah, New Jersey*, London.
- [23] Virella G and Tomlinson S (2007). Infection and immunity. In: Virella G. Eds. *Medical immunity*, 6th edn. *Information Healthcare*, NewYork, 183-200.
- [24] Norouzi R.A, Noreddin A and Elzowalaty M.E (2019). Scolicidal effect of nanoparticles against hydatid cyst protoscolices in vitro. *International Journal of Nano medicine*, 15: 1095-1100.
- [25] Liu Y, Wang X, Ren W, Chen Y, Yu Y, Zhang J, Bawudong D, Gu J, Xu X and Zhang X (2013). Novel albendazole – chitosan nanoparticles for intestinal absorption enhancement and hepatic targeting improvement in rats. *Journal Biomedical Material and Research Part. B*, 101: 998-1005.
- [26] Moazeini M, Borji H, Darbandi M, Jamal saharhiz M (2017). In vitro and in vivo antihydatid activity of Nano emulsion of Zataria multiflora essential oil. *Research in Veterinary science*, 114: 303–312.
- [27] Torabi N, Dobakhti F, Faghihzadeh S and Haniloo A (2018). In vitro and in vivo effects of chitosan – praziquantel and chitosan – albendazole nanoparticles on Echinococcus granulosus metacestodes . *Parasitology Research*, 117.
- [28] Mahmoudvand H, Harandi M.F, Shakibaie M and Aflatoonian M (2014). Scolicidal effects of biogenic selenium nanoparticles against protoscolices of hydatid cysts. *International Journal of Surgery*, 4: 374-377.
- [29] Ahmadpour E, Godrati Z, Spotin A, Norouzi R, Hamishehkar H, Nami S, Heydarian P, Rajabi S, Mohammadi M and Perez–cordong (2019). Nanostructure lipid carriers of ivermectin as a novel drug delivery system in hydatidosis. *Journal of Parasites and Vectors*, 12: 469.
- [30] San Y, Chen D, Pan Y, Qu W, Hao H, Wang X, Liu Z and Xie S (2019). Nanoparticles for antiparasitic drug delivery. *Iranian Journal of drug delivery*, 1: 1206-1221.
- [31] Liang W, Wang XC, Zhang SJ, Sun H, Max X and Peng XY (2014). Efficacy of albendazole–chitosan microspheres against Echinococcus granulosus infection in mice. *National Center for Biotechnology Information*, 3: 188-92.
- [32] Farhadi M, Haniloo A, Rostamizadeh K and Faghihzadeh S (2018). Efficiency of flubendazole-loaded Mpeg-PCL nanoparticles: A promising formulation against the protoscolices and cysts of Echinococcus granulosus. *Acta tropica*, 187.
- [33] Cong T, Tri, Faivre V, Nauyen TT, Heras H, Pirot F, Walchshofer N, Sarciron M and Falson F (2008). Study on the hydatid cyst membrane: permeation of model molecules and interactions with drug- loaded nanoparticles. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 2: 223-232.